

Awareness and Perception of Sustainable Development Goals on Application of Technology and Innovative Teaching among Primary School Teachers in Ilorin Metropolis

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Abstract

This study examined the awareness and perception of sustainable development goals (SDGs) and their influence on the application of technology and innovative teaching among primary school teachers in Ilorin Metropolis. A descriptive survey design was adopted, and a sample of 356 primary school teachers (178 Male, 178 Female) was drawn using stratified random sampling from a population of 4,829 primary school teachers (2,414 Male, 2,415 Female) in Ilorin metropolis during the 2023/2024 academic session. The instrument for data collection was a 32-item Sustainable Development Goals Perception Scale (SDGsPS) adapted by the researcher, and the reliability of the instrument was established using the test-retest technique, yielding a coefficient index of 0.81 using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) reliability test. Mean (\bar{x}) and t-test were used to answer research questions and test hypotheses respectively. The results revealed a moderate level of awareness of SDGs among primary teachers in Ilorin Metropolis. While there was a relatively low extent of technology use for SDGs, primary school teachers in Ilorin Metropolis showed a relatively high extent of employing innovative teaching methods for SDGs. Recommendations include the need for adequate provision of funds and other educational resources, and the integration of primary school teachers into the entire process of the SDGs program to achieve the objectives effectively. Additionally, school administrators should support and facilitate teachers' participation in workshops focused on SDGs, technology, and innovative teaching methods, while teacher training institutions should integrate SDGs into teacher training curricula to ensure future educators are well-prepared for sustainable development education.

Keywords: Innovative Teaching Methods, Teachers' Level of Perception, School Type, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Introduction

The history of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) can be traced back to the United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development, also known as Rio+20, held in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil in 2012. The conference aimed to promote sustainable development and integrate economic, social, and environmental objectives. At Rio+20, Member States agreed to develop a set of sustainable development goals that would build on the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) adopted in 2000, which aimed to reduce poverty and improve social development outcomes (UNO 2012).

Specifically, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are a set of 17 global goals consist of 169 target adopted by the United Nations in 2015, aimed at addressing poverty, inequality, and climate change to create a better future for all (UNDP, 2015). The SDGs build on the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and aim to achieve a sustainable and equitable world by 2030. The SDGs address a broad range of issues, including ending poverty and hunger, improving health and education, promoting gender equality, providing access to clean water and sanitation, promoting sustainable economic growth, and reducing inequality. Additionally, the goals cover environmental issues such as climate change, biodiversity, and sustainable consumption and production (UNO, 2021).

The goals are interrelated and interconnected, and achieving them requires the cooperation and participation of governments, civil society, the private sector, and individuals. The goals provide a framework for action, and each goal has specific targets and indicators to measure progress towards achieving them (United Nations, 2021). By implication, it could be said that effective implementation of the program demands enhanced capacity of the populace and inclusivity of diverse sectors of society (Idialu, 2022).

In the light of the above, it is obvious that education play a critical role in achieving sustainable development goals (SDGs). Education serves as an important means of implementation for sustainable human development due to the number of positive benefits it brings across the development goals. Education is the key to the global integrated framework of sustainable development goals. Education is at the heart of our efforts both to adapt to change and to transform the world within which we live. A quality basic education is the necessary foundation for learning throughout life in a complex and rapidly changing world

(UNESCO, 2015). According to the United Nations' Organization (UNO, 2021), education empowers the citizenry to transform the society by re-orienting them to develop the requisite knowledge, skills and attitudes for sustainable development. Through effective teaching and learning, the learners are gradually equipped to face the demands of a more sustainable world.

Similarly, educating for the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) requires revision of education policies and curriculum. This includes revising the National Policy on Education, improving curriculum content, providing sufficient instructional resources, increasing funding, and enhancing capacity building for teachers. Primary school teachers, in particular, have a significant responsibility to contribute to the attainment of the SDGs. The success of any educational program depends heavily on the quality of teachers. Therefore, teachers at all levels are considered the central figures in any educational process. It is imperative that primary school teachers are not only aware of the national and global educational demands but are also equipped with the necessary skills and knowledge to tailor their teaching to these demands.

As stated in the 2013 Federal Ministry of Education (FME) report, the quality of teachers in any educational system greatly affects the quality of teaching and learning in the system. Therefore, it is essential to prioritize the professional development of primary school teachers and ensure they have access to the resources needed to enhance their effectiveness.

Specifically, teacher perceptions according to IRIS Center (2012) are the thoughts or mental images teachers have about their students which are shaped by their background knowledge and life experiences. Teachers' perceptions can be influenced by a variety of factors, including their own experiences, training, beliefs, and values, as well as external factors such as school policies, societal expectations, and cultural norms. However, there are some common perceptions that teachers have on the use of technology and innovative teaching methods. One of the most common perceptions among teachers is that technology can be a valuable tool for teaching and learning. Many teachers recognize the potential of technology to engage students and make learning more interactive and meaningful.

Basically, use of technology for educational purposes yield positive outcomes on the part of the students such as increased motivation, active learning, providing efficient resources and better access to information (Sahin-Kizil, 2011). In the same vein, Wang and Woo (2007) also reviewed that technology has great potential to increase learners' motivation, link learners to various information sources, support collaborative learning, and allow teachers more time for facilitation in classrooms. Thus, when considering the use of technology, it should not simply be employed because it is readily available or because it has demonstrated effectiveness in certain circumstances. Instead, the purpose of utilizing technology should be to facilitate the learning process and enhance educational outcomes. Reflections on the use of technology should therefore concentrate on evaluating the appropriateness of the technology used, as well as identifying its strengths and weaknesses, and determining possible areas for improvement.

In the context of educating and acquiring knowledge, innovation involves deliberate application of information, imaginations and initiatives in deriving greater or different values from resources which often results when new ideas are applied to satisfy the needs and expectations of students (Author, 2013). In other words, innovative teaching methods in the teaching-learning process refer to new methods and means of teaching in an educational sector to achieve set instructional goals and objective (Aja, Eze, Igba & Elom, 2017). Hence, some of the innovative teaching methods as considered in this study are: Individualized instruction, simulation and game, team teaching, language laboratory and power point presentation.

To this end, education as an agent of behavioural change becomes the major driver of achieving these sustainable development goals. This is because education is the training of the mind to become functional member of the society (Animba, 2021). Hence, education provides a better platform for these changes through teacher-learner relationship. Talk is always cheap however application is difficult hence the need for education for solving these sustainable development goals. This is important in order for human resolution to get to the different strata and class for effective and efficient implementation of these goals.

The above however, calls to mind, the words of Westermann & Venegas (2017), who affirmed that education for sustainable development requires participatory teaching and learning approaches in order to motivate teachers and empower learners to change their behaviour and take action in order for sustainable development to be achieved. In a broader sense, Nsofer and Ahmed (2015) maintained that the teacher must structure a variety of learning styles, interacts, and abilities using computer programme and instructions, computer assisted instructions and numerous types of multimedia resources that deliver text, audio, graphics, animation, narrations, sound and streaming video in order to achieve high with these techniques. Thus, the integration of technologies and innovative teaching methods can help teachers and students to improve and develop the quality of education by providing curricular support in difficult subject areas (Gulbahar and Guven, 2008). In support of this finding, Wheeler (2000) discovers that technology improves efficiency in the educational process and effect changes in teaching methodology, assessment of learning, student tracking, communication and evaluation.

In contrast however, Yusuf (2005) and Olulube (2006) report in their studies that teachers' technology competence in Nigeria is below expectation. This finding corroborates the research finding to Chike-Okoli and Gambabri (2007) who find out

that only a negligible number of vocational and technological teachers make use of ICT in teaching, learning and school management.

Consequently, one begins to wonder how well the integration of technologies and innovative teaching methods will help in achieving Sustainable Developmental Goals (SDG 4). In order to achieve the sustainable development goals effectively, it is crucial to understand the perspectives of key stakeholders involved in curriculum implementation and assess the efficient utilization of technology and innovative teaching method towards attaining these goals. Thus, it is essential to assess the perception of SDGs among primary school teachers, particularly regarding technology usage and innovative teaching strategies, to ensure their effective implementation and alignment with sustainable development priorities. This state of the problem aims to shed light on the current situation in Kwara State, Nigeria, regarding primary school teachers' perception of SDGs, technology usage, and innovative teaching approaches.

In order to achieve the sustainable development goals effectively, it is crucial to understand the perspectives of key stakeholders involved in curriculum implementation and assess the efficient management of human and material resources towards attaining these goals.

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are a set of global objectives established by the United Nations to address various social, economic, and environmental challenges and promote sustainable development worldwide. Achieving these goals requires active participation from all sectors of society, including the education sector. In Nigeria, particularly in Kwara State, primary school teachers play a crucial role in shaping the future of the country by imparting knowledge and values to young learners.

However, the effective integration of technology usage and innovative teaching methods in primary schools is vital to meet the demands of the 21st-century learning environment and contribute to the attainment of the SDGs. Technology can enhance teaching and learning experiences, promote critical thinking skills, and foster creativity among students. Additionally, innovative teaching approaches can help address the diverse learning needs of students and promote active engagement in the learning process.

Despite the potential benefits, the extent to which primary school teachers in Ilorin Metropolis perceive and incorporate the SDGs, technology usage, and innovative teaching methods into their pedagogical practices remains unclear. This lack of understanding and utilization of technology and innovative teaching approaches may hinder the effective implementation of the SDGs in the education system, impeding progress towards sustainable development.

Therefore, it is crucial to investigate the perception of primary school teachers in Kwara State regarding the SDGs, their knowledge and utilization of technology in the classroom, and their adoption of innovative teaching methods. Understanding these factors will provide valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities faced by teachers in integrating technology and innovative approaches to support the achievement of the SDGs. Additionally, exploring the perceptions of teachers can help identify gaps in training and support, inform policy decisions, and guide the development of professional development programs that enhance teachers' capacity to utilize technology and innovative teaching methods effectively. By addressing these gaps in knowledge and practice, this study aims to contribute to the improvement of primary education in Ilorin Metropolis and the overall achievement of the SDGs.

Objectives of the study

The objective of this study is to assess the awareness and perception of sustainable development goals (SDGs) and their influence on the application of technology and innovative teaching among primary school teachers in Ilorin Metropolis. Specifically, the study is aimed at finding out the:

1. Extent to which primary school teachers are aware of sustainable development goals concerning the use of technology and innovative teaching methods in Ilorin Metropolis.
2. Extent to which primary school teachers use technology in their teaching for attainment of SDGs in Ilorin Metropolis.
3. Extent to which primary school teachers use innovative methods in their teaching for attainment of SDGs in Ilorin Metropolis.

Research Questions

The following research questions are raised to guide the study:

1. To what extent are primary school teachers aware of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) concerning the use of technology and innovative teaching methods in Ilorin Metropolis?
2. To what extent do primary school teachers use of technology in their teaching for attainment of SDGs in Ilorin Metropolis?

3. To what extent do primary school teachers use of innovative teaching methods for attainment of SDGs in Ilorin Metropolis?

Research Hypotheses

The study was anchored on the following hypotheses:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean perception of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) between primary school male and female teachers regarding technology usage and innovative teaching methods in Ilorin Metropolis.
2. There is no significant difference in primary school teachers' mean level of perception of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) regarding technology usage and innovative teaching methods by years of teaching experience in Ilorin Metropolis.

Methodology

The research design adopted for the study is survey research design. The reason for adopting this design was to solely obtain information from the respondents about the existing situation in the study area. Population of the study comprised all the 4,226 primary school teachers (2,414 Male, 2,415 Female) in 18 public primary schools in Ilorin Metropolis of Kwara State, Nigeria (Planning, Research and Statistics Department SUBEB, 2022). Primary school teachers only were used for the study because they implement the curriculum at the primary school level and also close to the students at that level. However, the sample for the study comprised 356 respondents (178 Male, 178 Female). Simple random sampling technique precisely by balloting was employed to select 20 teachers each from the 18 public primary schools used for the study.

On the basis of the above sampling techniques, it is hoped that the sample reflected all the characteristics of all the teachers in all the public primary schools in Ilorin Metropolis. Specifically, the sample consisted of primary school teachers both in the urban and rural areas of the study area. The sample also consisted of both male and female primary school teachers and experienced and inexperienced teachers. In addition, the teachers were selected from different subjects' area of specialization in the selected public primary schools in Ilorin Metropolis.

For the study, a questionnaire called the Sustainable Development Goals Perception Scale (SDGsPS) was utilized as the research instrument. The researcher adapted this questionnaire after conducting a thorough review of relevant literature. To ensure its validity, the preliminary version of the questionnaire was reviewed and validated by a panel of experts. The panel consisted of two experienced lecturers and two experts in Test and Measurement from Universities. The observations and suggestions made by experts were used for the final preparation of the instrument.

In computing the reliability of this research instrument, test-retest technique was used to determine the reliability of the instrument using data from the pilot study carried out on 20 participants outside the sample size. A reliability index of 0.72 was established using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient which is high, reliable and adequate for a standardized instrument. However, mean (\bar{x}) and t-test were used to answer research questions and test hypotheses respectively.

Results

In line with the study's research questions and hypotheses, the findings are outlined below.

Research Question 1:

To what extent are primary school teachers aware of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) concerning the use of technology and innovative teaching methods in Ilorin Metropolis?

Table 1: Extent of Primary School Teachers' Awareness of the Sustainable Development Goals Concerning the Use of Technology and Innovative Teaching Methods

S/No	Items	Mean (\bar{X})	SD	Remarks
1	The Sustainable Development Goals is clearly spelt out as regard the use of technology and innovative teaching methods.	2.51	1.02	Agree
2	The teacher had good knowledge of the interpretation of the Sustainable Development Goals.	2.67	1.14	Agree
3	The awareness of the 17 aspirational Sustainable Development Goals is universal among teachers.	2.31	0.62	Disagree
4	The Sustainable Development Goals are designed to be action-oriented before they can be achieved.	2.55	1.10	Disagree

5	Teacher had good understanding of the Sustainable Development Goals content.	2.49	0.71	Agree
Grand Mean		2.51	0.92	Agreed

Source: Author’s Computation, 2024

Table 1 illustrates the awareness level of primary teachers regarding the integration of technology and innovative teaching methods aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals. Scores for all categories of primary teachers exceed the cut-off mean of 2.50. Consequently, the grand mean of 2.51 succinctly denotes a moderate level of awareness of Sustainable Development Goals among the primary teachers.

Research Question 2:

To what extent do primary school teachers use of technology in their teaching for attainment of SDGs in Ilorin Metropolis?

Table 2: Extent to which primary school teachers in Ilorin Metropolis use of technology for attainment of SDGs

S/No	Items	Mean (\bar{X})	SD	Remarks
1	Teachers frequently incorporate technology tools in their daily lesson plans to address Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in the classroom.	2.16	0.42	Disagree
2	I have high proficiency in using educational technology platforms to enhance teaching practices related to SDGs.	2.45	0.54	Disagree
3	Teacher utilizes digital resources, such as online educational materials or applications, to support SDGs in your teaching.	2.33	0.72	Disagree
4	My students are encouraging to use technology tools for independent research or projects related to SDGs.	2.10	0.60	Disagree
5	Teacher adapts and integrate new and emerging technologies into your teaching methods to promote awareness and understanding of SDGs.	2.27	0.58	Disagree
Grand Mean		2.26	0.57	Low Extent

Source: Author’s Computation, 2024

Table 2 illustrates the utilization of technology by primary school teachers in Ilorin Metropolis for achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Scores across all categories of primary teachers fall below the established cut-off mean of 2.50. Accordingly, the grand mean of 2.26 concisely indicates a relatively low extent to which primary school teachers in Ilorin Metropolis use technology for the attainment of SDGs.

Research Question 3:

To what extent do primary school teachers use of innovative teaching methods for attainment of SDGs in Ilorin Metropolis?

Table 3: Extent to which primary school teachers in Ilorin Metropolis use of innovative teaching methods for attainment of SDGs

S/No	Items	Mean (\bar{X})	SD	Remarks
1	I integrate the use of technology tools and multimedia elements to enhance innovative teaching approaches in relation to SDGs.	2.67	1.02	Agree
2	I incorporate experiential learning activities, such as field trips or hands-on projects, to deepen students' engagement with SDG concepts.	2.55	0.98	Agree
3	Teachers frequently integrate real-world scenarios and case studies related to SDGs into your teaching materials.	2.83	1.22	Agree
4	Teacher to a high extent employs collaborative learning strategies to enhance students' understanding of SDGs and promote teamwork in achieving sustainable outcomes.	2.71	1.10	Agree
5	Teachers frequently incorporate project-based learning methods to address Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in their primary school classroom.	2.73	1.13	Agree

Grand Mean

2.70

1.09

High Extent

Source: Author's Computation, 2024

Table 3 illustrates the implementation of innovative teaching methods by primary school teachers in Ilorin Metropolis for achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Scores across all categories of primary teachers surpass the established cut-off mean of 2.50. Consequently, the grand mean of 2.70 succinctly indicates a relatively high extent to which primary school teachers in Ilorin Metropolis employ innovative teaching methods for the attainment of SDGs.

Research Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant difference in the mean perception of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) between primary school male and female teachers regarding technology usage and innovative teaching methods in Ilorin Metropolis.

Table 4: Summary of t-test analysis of the mean level of perception of Sustainable Development Goals among Primary School Teachers on Technology Usage and Innovative Teaching by gender

Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-value	Sig	Decision
Male	178	18.3	0.58	351	1.68	0.071	Not Sig.
Female	175	18.1	0.56				

Source: Author's Computation, 2024.

Analysis from table 4 indicates that the computed t-value is 1.68 at a degree of freedom of 351 with a probability value of 0.071. Since the computed probability value (p-value) of 0.071 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, the stated null hypothesis is therefore accepted. Meaning that, there is no significant difference in the mean perception of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) between primary school male and female teachers regarding technology usage and innovative teaching methods.

Research Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant difference in primary school teachers' mean level of perception of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) regarding technology usage and innovative teaching methods by years of teaching experience in Ilorin Metropolis.

Table 5: Summary of t-test analysis of the mean level of perception of Sustainable Development Goals among Primary School Teachers on Technology Usage and Innovative Teaching by years of teaching experience

Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-value	Sig	Decision
Experienced Teacher	178	19.1	0.83	351	2.98	0.013	Sig.
Inexperienced Teacher	175	18.4	0.97				

Source: Author's Computation, 2024

Analysis from table 5 indicates that the computed t-value is 2.98 at a degree of freedom of 351 with a probability value of 0.013. Since the computed probability value (p-value) of 0.013 is less than the 0.05 level of significance, the stated null hypothesis is therefore rejected. Meaning that, there is no significant difference in the mean perception of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) among primary school teachers regarding technology usage and innovative teaching methods by years of teaching experience.

Discussion of Findings

The first finding of the study revealed that there is a moderate level of awareness of Sustainable Development Goals among the primary teachers. It might be attributed to insufficient integration of SDG-related content in teacher training programs, limited professional development opportunities focusing on SDGs, or inadequate dissemination of information about SDGs within the educational system. This finding is supported by Agbi (2022) who reported that science lecturers have a mere moderate level of awareness of the SDGs programme, there has not been adequate advocacy by government and its agencies as regards the SDGs programme. Hence, limited awareness of SDGs among Nigerian primary teachers may hinder effective teaching of sustainable development to students, impacting broader societal understanding and commitment to sustainability. Addressing this gap is crucial for successful SDG integration in Kwara state education system.

The study unveiled in its second finding that there is low extent to which primary school teachers use technology for the attainment of SDGs in Ilorin Metropolis. This may result from inadequate access to technology infrastructure and

insufficient training on integrating technology into teaching practices. The finding of the study is in agreement with Yusuf (2005) and Olulube (2006) in Akpan (2008) found out that teachers' ICT competence in Nigeria is below expectation. So, most teachers do not recognize the potentials of ICT and as such the impact of ICT in teaching and learning is considered to be limited. This implies that low use of technology in class may hinder effective delivery of SDG-related content to students, impacting their awareness and skills in sustainable development.

The study's third discovery revealed a relatively high extent to which primary school teachers in Ilorin Metropolis employ innovative teaching methods for the attainment of SDGs. This finding might be influenced by collaborative initiatives and peer-sharing platforms among teachers for exchange of innovative teaching ideas which contributed to the overall adoption of these methods in the context of SDG implementation. This finding correspond with the work of Knutson (2014) who pointed out that choosing the appropriate approaches in teaching and how these approaches are made is pertinent to students' learning. The implications may result in enhanced student engagement, a more effective understanding of sustainable development concepts, and better preparation of students to contribute meaningfully to SDGs.

In the fourth finding of this study, it was revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean perception of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) between primary school male and female teachers regarding technology usage and innovative teaching methods. This may be credited to a uniform integration of technology and innovative teaching practices in teacher training programs. This finding corroborates with the work of Saltan (2016) who reported difference between ICT selection criteria such as ICT ease of use in terms of gender as an indicator but the difference is statistically insignificant. This suggests a positive outcome in terms of gender equity in the awareness and application of sustainable development principles within the teaching community, fostering a more inclusive and equitable educational environment.

The study's fifth discovery unveiled that there is no significant difference in the mean perception of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) among primary school teachers regarding technology usage and innovative teaching methods by years of teaching experience. The finding may be influenced by the varying exposure and adaptability to evolving teaching methods over time. Teachers with more experience may have undergone different professional development opportunities, making them more receptive to incorporating technology and innovative teaching approaches aligned with sustainable development. This finding concurs with assertion of Agbi (2022) who revealed that experienced science lecturers have higher perception of the SDGs programme than their inexperienced counterparts. This finding implies that tailored professional development programs catering to varying levels of teaching experience may be necessary.

Conclusion

In summary, the study reveals a moderate awareness of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) among primary school teachers in Ilorin Metropolis, with challenges in low technology usage but a positive trend in innovative teaching methods. Gender does not significantly affect SDG perceptions, but differences based on teaching experience suggest the need for tailored professional development. These findings emphasize the diverse factors influencing SDG integration, calling for strategic interventions to enhance awareness, technology use, and innovative teaching practices among primary school teachers.

Recommendations

1. Government and Education Authorities should launch targeted awareness campaigns within primary teacher communities to improve Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) understanding, and invest in technology infrastructure and training programs to empower primary teachers in Kwara State for effective SDG integration.
2. Teacher Training Institutions should integrate SDGs into teacher training curricula, ensuring future educators are well-prepared for sustainable development education.
3. Professional Development Providers should customize professional development sessions to cater to the unique needs of primary teachers, emphasizing SDGs, technology usage, and innovative teaching methods.
4. School Administrators should support and facilitate teachers' participation in workshops focused on SDGs, technology, and innovative teaching methods.
5. Teachers should actively engage in SDG, technology, and innovative teaching training opportunities, and form professional communities to share experiences and strategies for successful integration.

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